

Assessing opportunities and inequities in undergraduate ecological forecasting education

Alyssa M. Willson, Hayden Gallo, Jody A. Peters, Antoinette Abeyta, Nievita Bueno Watts, Cayelan C. Carey, Tadhg N. Moore, Georgia Smies, R. Quinn Thomas, Whitney M. Woelmer, Jason S. McLachlan

Abstract

Ecological forecasting (EF) has become important for predicting the future state of ecosystems and their services and offers a promising approach for introducing a diverse group of researchers to quantitative methods in ecology. Making ecological forecasts that address complex, real-world problems requires a diverse, quantitatively-trained EF workforce, which begins with equitably training students in EF and quantitative skills at the undergraduate level. Understanding the current undergraduate curriculum landscape in ecology and environmental sciences (EES) allows for targeted interventions to improve equitable educational opportunities. To characterize the current state of forecasting education, we compiled existing resources for teaching and learning EF at three curriculum levels (open-access, online resources, OAORs; U.S. university courses on EF; and U.S. university courses on topics related to EF). We found persistent patterns (1) in what topics are taught to U.S. undergraduate students at each of the curriculum levels; and (2) in the accessibility of resources, in terms of course availability at higher education institutions in the U.S. We developed and implemented programs to increase the accessibility and comprehensiveness of EF undergraduate education, including initiatives to engage specifically with Native American undergraduates and open-access resources for learning quantitative concepts at the undergraduate level. Such steps enhance the capacity of EF to be more inclusive and expose more students to quantitative training.

Introduction

Undergraduate ecology education prepares the next generation of scientists to address the complex environmental problems facing 21st century society. Increasingly, environmental and ecological problem-solving requires using quantitative (Barraquand et al., 2014; Farrell and Carey, 2018) and interdisciplinary (Boon and Van Baalen, 2018; National Academies of Sciences, National Academy of Engineering, and Institute of Medicine, 2005) research methods and skills. Introducing undergraduate students to sub-disciplines of ecology that focus on quantitative and interdisciplinary skills can increase students' preparedness to contribute to ecological and environmental research and problem solving in graduate school and in their careers (Farrell and Carey, 2018; Hounshell et al., 2021). Not only should education focus on training students broadly in quantitative and interdisciplinary methods, but also there is a strong need for targeted efforts that promote educational equity and inclusivity. Providing opportunities to students who would not traditionally receive quantitative and interdisciplinary training enables a greater diversity of scientists to contribute more diverse ideas and perspectives which will inherently represent more diverse stakeholder interests (Bowser and Cid, 2021; Cheryan et al., 2017; Gardner-Vandy et al., 2021; Graham et al., 2013; Hofstra et al., 2020; Kozlowski

et al., 2022; Morrison and Steltzer, 2021; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021a). Numerous recent publications have highlighted the continued lack of diversity among science students and professionals (Hunter et al., 2010; Miriti, 2021, 2019; Riegle-Crumb et al., 2019; Schell et al., 2020), particularly in quantitative and data science fields (Paxton, 2020), and urged for greater attention to how to improve the equity of science education, as one component of addressing this pervasive problem.

We contend that ecological forecasting (EF) provides an opportunity to address 21st century environmental and ecological challenges (Box 1). Making accurate, quantitative forecasts about the future state of ecosystems is an urgent need to improve scientific understanding of ecological phenomena and to implement appropriate policy and management decisions (Dietze, 2017a). Examples of quantitative ecological forecasts include forecasts of the global carbon cycle (Gao et al., 2011), water quality forecasts (Carey et al., 2022), and epidemiological forecasts (Oidtman et al., 2021), each of which informs policy and management. To keep pace with the growing demand for forecasts, an increasing number and diversity of scientists must be available to contribute to the discipline, meaning that more scientists must be familiar with, or even have expert knowledge on, EF, including quantitative and interdisciplinary ecological methods. Despite its importance for 21st century policy and management (Bradford et al., 2020), EF is currently regarded as a niche topic taught to graduate students and is seldom taught at the undergraduate level.

EF not only can help address complex environmental problems, but also offers a unique approach to undergraduate education, in which key concepts and skills, including quantitative skills and interdisciplinary team building, can be taught under a unifying framework (Box 1). We take an approach to EF consistent with the Ecological Forecasting Initiative (EFI; Dietze and Lynch, 2019), strongly influenced by the work of (Dietze, 2017b). This approach is grounded in the disciplines of ecology and statistics, consistent with the tradition of predictive ecology, but additionally promotes the integration of social sciences with these disciplines to improve the applicability of forecasts to end users, for example, and the implementation of an iterative approach to EF with iterative data assimilation. As an emerging sub-field with an active scholarly community, there are numerous opportunities to consider how to make EF more inclusive and equitable to students and professionals from underrepresented backgrounds. For these reasons, EF, an emerging sub-field with a suite of pedagogical benefits for undergraduate students (Box 1), offers a timely opportunity to consider how to revise and expand the existing ecology and environmental sciences (EES) curriculum to better meet the needs of undergraduate students and the science workforce post graduation.

Box 1: Ecological Forecasting

What is ecological forecasting?

Ecological forecasting (EF) is the process of producing quantitative predictions for an unknown state of an ecosystem or its services with quantified uncertainty (Carey et al., 2021; Clark et al., 2001). This sub-field integrates theory and methods from multiple

disciplines outside of ecology, including data science (e.g., through the use and manipulation of large datasets), computer science (e.g., through the development of automated workflows for iteratively running software), statistics (e.g., through the development of statistical models), and social sciences (e.g., through the use of forecasts as applied decision support tools in management contexts) (Woelmer et al., 2021). EF is a relatively new, emerging sub-field (Dietze, 2017a; Lewis et al., 2022), meaning that opportunities for learning EF are relatively infrequent, but also that opportunities to develop curricula at the undergraduate level and to consider the equity of EF education are abundant.

Why teach and learn ecological forecasting?

Teaching undergraduate students ecology through the perspective of EF can offer instructors a way to integrate multiple pedagogical benefits in a unifying framework. Specifically, EF

1. Facilitates connections between scientific concepts

- EF introduces students to concepts from multiple disciplines (e.g., ecology, mathematics, social sciences) under a unifying framework (i.e., EF) that can promote interdisciplinary thinking for solving complex problems (Boon and Van Baalen, 2018) and student skillbuilding (Vogler et al., 2018)
- Learning about ecological modeling (a component of EF) has been shown to increase students' "systems thinking," or students' ability to recognize the interrelatedness of components of an ecological system, relative to a traditional ecology education (Carey et al., 2020)
- EF emphasizes quantitative skills, such as modeling, coding, and statistics, thus providing a means to introduce students to quantitative skills. The skills are useful for students interested in pursuing careers in any domain of science (Barraquand et al., 2014)
- EF encourages integration of the social sciences with the natural sciences, which can increase students' perceptions of the relevance of the natural sciences to their lives (Tripp and Shortlidge, 2019) and offers students an opportunity to navigate multiple stakeholders in applied science contexts (Parr et al., 2007)

2. Improves student engagement over traditional teaching methods

- EF emphasizes the real-world applications of interdisciplinary science training (Boon and Van Baalen, 2018), which facilitates instruction using project-based, active learning strategies that increase engagement (Graham et al., 2013; Vogler et al., 2018)
- Teaching EF using specific, case-based examples (see Discussion: Current EFI education initiatives) presents the opportunity to offer students culturally-relevant curriculum (Harris et al., 2020), which promotes

engagement and persistence particularly among students from underrepresented backgrounds (Corneille et al., 2020; Gardner-Vandy et al., 2021)

3. Prepares students for the scientific workforce

- Iterative EF, in which model predictions representing ecological hypotheses are repeatedly confronted with data, represents one of the most rigorous tests of ecological theory (Dietze, 2017b). Students with a background in EF enter the workforce with a suite of tools well suited to advancing scientific theory through iterative forecasts
- Predicting the state of ecosystems and their services under specific climate and management scenarios offers students the means to provide policymakers and stakeholders with a tool for making policy and management decisions
- EF offers students an opportunity to become familiar with the unique benefits and challenges of contributing to interdisciplinary research, which has become increasingly in-demand as complex global change problems require interdisciplinary solutions (Committee on Advancing a Systems Approach to Studying the Earth: A Strategy for the National Science Foundation et al., 2022; National Academies of Sciences, National Academy of Engineering, and Institute of Medicine, 2005).

Despite persistent calls over decades for increasing attention to be given to quantitative, predictive ecology (Clark et al., 2001; Dietze, 2017a; Houlihan et al., 2017; Jørgensen, 2002), undergraduate students in domain sciences (e.g., biology) are often not sufficiently introduced to quantitative methods to contribute to this body of research (Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018). Many higher education institutions do not require the quantitative coursework within biology and environmental science majors that currently serves as the foundation for EF, with quantitative coursework only offered in other disciplines, without collaboration with domain science instructors (Farrell and Carey, 2018; Robeva et al., 2020). Similarly, courses on high-level quantitative concepts, such as mechanistic modeling, are infrequently taught at the undergraduate level to ecology students. Similarly, at the time of publication and to the authors' knowledge, fewer than fifteen courses on EF are offered across the U.S. (Appendix Table 1.1), according to both our use of self-reported courses on EF through EFI and through a search for EF courses in the course catalogs of U.S. land-grant institutions (Appendix). This results in baccalaureate graduates who may be underprepared to contribute to research addressing 21st century global environmental problems, such as EF research.

In addition to relying on quantitative methods, addressing 21st century ecological research questions requires diverse teams of scientists and stakeholders. Having diverse research teams presents multiple benefits for science and society (*Enhancing the Effectiveness of Team Science*, 2015). Researchers from historically underrepresented groups tend to make more novel connections between scientific concepts (Hofstra et al., 2020; Kozlowski et al., 2022; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine,

2021a), suggesting that more diverse research teams produce more innovative research. Increasing the diversity of scientists also means that the identities of those working on issues such as climate change better represent the identities of the people affected by the same issues (Bowser and Cid, 2021). Finally, recruiting students from historically underrepresented groups into the scientific workforce increases the number of qualified and talented workers (Cheryan et al., 2017; Graham et al., 2013). These reasons to promote diversity within scientific disciplines operate concurrently with the more important perspective that diverse research teams are morally good (Morrison and Steltzer, 2021; National Research Council, Division of Earth and Life Studies, Board of Life Sciences, Committee on Undergraduate Biology Education to Prepare Research Scientists for the 21st Century, 2003); the worthiness of diverse research teams should not rely on the commodification of the contributions of scientists from underrepresented backgrounds (Gardner-Vandy et al., 2021). Making concerted efforts to improve the equity of educational opportunities represents a promising way to improve the persistence of students from diverse backgrounds into scientific disciplines (Graham et al., 2013).

Unfortunately, numerous barriers hinder the attainment of equitable science education and career opportunities in the United States. At the undergraduate level, students from marginalized ethnicities and genders show lower persistence in undergraduate science majors than White male students (Bowser and Cid, 2021). Factors contributing to the persistence disparity include, among many other inequities, a general lack of culturally relevant science curriculum (Collins, 2018; Corneille et al., 2020; Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018) and inequality in access to higher education resources (Dolcini et al., 2021; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021b; Sanders and Scanlon, 2021). Because ecology and environmental science research and curriculum has largely been constructed using a White, Western framework (David-Chavez and Gavin, 2018), scientific topics covered in coursework, the examples used to contextualize the information, and even what scientific questions we choose to ask can be irrelevant and inaccessible to students from marginalized backgrounds (Reano, 2019). Compounding these problems, science education can be inaccessible to students without consistent access to the Internet or to computer hardware often required for homework and online learning, and students without access to these resources are disproportionately from marginalized backgrounds (Dolcini et al., 2021; Sanders and Scanlon, 2021). Similarly, elite institutions of higher education, where instructors are more likely to have disciplinary expertise in emerging research sub-fields such as EF, disproportionately enroll White students (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021b), meaning students from marginalized backgrounds may not have the ability to enroll in courses on topics such as EF.

Here, we use EF to consider how to revise EES undergraduate education in the U.S. to meet the demands of the 21st century scientific workforce. Because EF is an emerging sub-field (Woelmer et al., 2021), there are few existing educational resources specific to EF, making resource development a high priority for the EF community. Consistent with recommendations from the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine on recruiting workers into the scientific workforce (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021b), we specifically emphasize developing equitable educational opportunities for undergraduate students. Leveraging these attributes of EF as an emerging, quantitative and interdisciplinary sub-field, we evaluate how EF can be used

as an opportunity to update and revise undergraduate EES curriculum in a way that simultaneously emphasizes quantitative skills and promotes educational equity.

The term “curriculum” encompasses many aspects of education, including educational materials, courses, and classroom practices, to name a few. Here, we focus on teaching and learning materials at three levels: (1) open-access, online materials on EF and related disciplines; (2) lessons (as defined in the calendars of course syllabi) within U.S. university-level courses specifically on the topic of EF (hereafter, forecasting course lessons); and (3) U.S. university-level courses on topics related to EF (hereafter, forecasting-adjacent courses). Examples of forecasting-adjacent courses include courses on the topics of ecology, statistics, computer science, informatics, and social science (i.e., expert elicitation and decision science). We envision that forecasting-adjacent courses could comprise an interdisciplinary EF degree program when combined. We focus on these curriculum levels because each fills a unique role in undergraduate education, offering a different combination of how many students can be reached (as well as the diversity of students reached) and the depth to which the material can be covered (Figure 1A).

We view curriculum revisions as activities that meaningfully deviate from the current undergraduate ecology curriculum. The standard undergraduate EES curriculum is characterized as focusing on conceptual, theory-based learning, as is available in most standard ecology textbooks (Klemow et al., 2019), while quantitative and computational skillbuilding (Farrell and Carey, 2018), as well as interdisciplinary thinking (Weathers et al., 2016), are often neglected despite calls to increase training in these areas (Klemow et al., 2019; Weathers et al., 2016). This includes providing students with more quantitative education (via the use of, e.g., open-access, online resources [OAORs] or courses on EF) and offering more interdisciplinary programs for students interested in interdisciplinary domains of science such as EF (via, e.g., forecasting-adjacent courses comprising an EF degree program). Finally, curriculum revision should include intentional strategies for making ecology and environmental science curriculum more inclusive to students from all racial/ethnic, gender, and socioeconomic backgrounds (via, e.g., programs to offer EF education to students from marginalized backgrounds).

One place to begin revising the existing EES curriculum is to understand the current curriculum landscape (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021a, 2020; Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018). Understanding what online materials and courses already exist allows educators to identify gaps in the existing EES curriculum to which finite time and resources could be allocated. We first assessed the existing educational resources for gaps in the EES curriculum at the three curriculum levels (Figure 1B). We focus on two aspects of the EES curriculum landscape via two questions. First, we address the question “What EF topics are being taught to undergraduate students, and what is not being taught that should be?” Second, we address the question “Who has access to the online resources and courses related to EF, based on social factors such as socioeconomic status and access to appropriate cyberinfrastructure?” In response, we discuss example programs the EF community has initiated to address the gaps we identified. We conclude with a discussion of future directions for the EF community, as well as limitations of our approach.

Methods

To examine the current state of EF undergraduate curriculum, we defined multiple curriculum levels (OAORs; forecasting course lessons; and forecasting-adjacent courses) (Methods: Description of Curriculum Levels). We collated resources available for teaching and learning EF at each curriculum level (Methods: Data Collection) and then compared the resources at each of the three curriculum levels, both in terms of how they are distributed among educational topics associated with a comprehensive EF education, and how accessible they are to students from diverse backgrounds and at diverse higher education institutions.

Description of Curriculum Levels

We defined multiple curriculum levels (OAORs; forecasting course lessons; and forecasting-adjacent courses), on which we collated available resources for teaching and learning EF (see Methods: Data collection). Each curriculum level has a different depth of material coverage and level of accessibility (Figure 1A). OAORs can be accessed by any student with a broadband Internet connection and a computer (high number of students reached), but online learning material can be limited to introductory material because these resources are often short in duration in comparison to semester-long courses and lack of student-instructor interface (shallow material coverage). In contrast, forecasting courses offer students in a classroom setting at limited institutions (low number of students reached) an overview of most of the necessary topics to become proficient in EF (moderate material coverage). Finally, forecasting-adjacent courses offer students across a given higher education institution (moderate number of students reached) an in-depth perspective on one or a few topics related to EF per course (in-depth material coverage) (Figure 1A). Combined, forecasting-adjacent courses could be used to develop an EF degree program within individual higher education institutions, although it is important to recognize the institutional barriers to this desired outcome, such as irrelevant or difficult prerequisites for courses related to EF, or conflicting visions for student learning objectives across disciplinary boundaries.

By open-access we mean that the resource was publicly available online, without the need to pay or ask permission to access the material. We define educational material as any course content, video, article, hands-on learning opportunity, code, or other online material that can be used to teach or learn about EF and adjacent topics (e.g., basic statistical techniques, foundational domain knowledge) (see Appendix Table 1.3 for a list of formats of educational material and their definitions). Our definition of OAORs ignores the contributions of massive open online courses (MOOCs), a growing platform for knowledge transfer to a large quantity of students (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2018). We chose to omit EF-related MOOCs from our analysis of OAORs to limit the complexity of our data collection and analysis procedures and we recognize that this choice impacts our characterization of OAORs as generally having shallow material coverage. We encourage future iterations of our analysis to consider the contribution of MOOCs to the ecology curriculum landscape.

Data Collection

We began our search for open-access, online educational material by using Google to search terms related to each of our EF topics (defined below, “Data Categorization”) in combination with terms such as “tutorial” and “learn” (e.g., “ecology tutorial,” “learn R”). These searches were conducted iteratively from July to December 2020. We supplemented our Google searches with searches of the course and lab websites of known instructors and practitioners of EF and quantitative ecology during the same time period. Finally, we created and distributed a Google Form through which we asked other members of the EF community to submit other known OAORs, which was disseminated via EFI communications (i.e., Slack, monthly newsletter, and via word-of-mouth during working group meetings) during 2020 (Figure 1B). A complete database of the compiled resources is available via QUBES (Willson and Peters, 2021). We acknowledge that our database of OAORs is incomplete because of the great number of resources available on the Internet, particularly for learning basic concepts such as statistical computing languages. However, we believe our database is a representative subsample of all resources available for learning EF because it was collated giving each forecasting topic equal attention (i.e., time and effort in searches).

We collated a list of forecasting courses from which we identified topics covered in individual course lessons. EFI, a grassroots organization focused on creating a community of practice around near-term EF, houses a database of known forecasting courses on its website (<https://ecoforecast.org/resources/educational-resources/>). The courses are largely self-identified, with instructors volunteering to include their syllabus on the website; when we knew of an EF course that was not on the website, we additionally asked individual instructors to submit their syllabus for inclusion on the website. As of March 15, 2022, the database includes nine courses at the undergraduate and/or graduate educational level that fall within our definition of a forecasting course and have a syllabus available online (Appendix 1). To ensure that we did not bias our sample by including only courses from the EFI website, we searched the course catalogs (i.e., including every department) of U.S. land grant institutions for potential EF courses and contacted the instructors of courses thought to be on EF. We chose to sample U.S. land grant institutions because this offered a representative subsample of all U.S. higher education institutions, with substantial representation of minority-serving institutions (e.g., hispanic-serving institutions, historically black colleges and universities, tribal colleges) and two-year colleges, as well as high and very high research intensity colleges and universities (Appendix 1). We found no additional courses on EF during this additional search (Appendix 1). Because we are aware of so few forecasting courses that match our criteria in the U.S., we chose to include both undergraduate and graduate courses in our analysis of forecasting course lessons. For each of these nine courses, we used the syllabus to determine what topics are taught during the course. Specifically, we categorized each lesson title from the course schedule into one of the topics of EF defined below (Figure 1B).

Finally, we compiled data on forecasting-adjacent courses available at a subset of 48 higher education institutions in the U.S. We randomly selected institutions from a list published by *The Edvocate* (Lynch, 2019). We chose this list because it represents a comprehensive list of all colleges and universities in the U.S., 1,900 higher education

institutions, including two-year and four-year colleges, private and public universities, and for-profit and not-for-profit institutions, and includes institutions from all fifty states. Sampling was not stratified, so our random subsample is representative of the relative frequency of different institution types (e.g., baccalaureate colleges, very high research intensity doctoral universities). For each institution, we systematically read the most recent course catalog and recorded undergraduate course names and descriptions related to EF and the forecasting topic (defined below) that best defines the content of the course. This procedure allowed us to assess whether most courses in each discipline were on EF, including many disciplinary seminars, by their course descriptions. However, some courses were inevitably missed with this procedure because course names and descriptions were sometimes unavailable, especially for upper-level seminars and special topics courses. More detailed explanations about the data collection procedure for each curriculum level are available in Appendix 1.

Data Categorization

We defined general topics that comprise EF, which we used to categorize the data we collected at each curriculum level. The topics represent the skills and concepts with which a student of EF should ideally become familiar during their education. We defined the forecasting topics via expert elicitation by multiple founding members of EFI, such that our topics represent EFI's current view of the requirements for a well-rounded education in EF. The topics represent skills and concepts from multiple disciplines, including biological sciences, computer science, statistics, and social sciences (Appendix Table 1.3). Our definition of forecasting topics using expert elicitation introduced bias in favor of the approach to EF promoted by EFI, as noted in the Introduction; this bias will be discussed in more detail below (Data analysis).

The purpose of defining EF topics was to assess the distribution of resources within broad categories of knowledge and skills students are currently learning from EF at the different curriculum levels. We classified each open-access, online resource into one or more topics that best represent the subject content. We classified each lesson from forecasting courses into one topic that best represents the material covered in the class for that lesson. Similarly, we categorized each forecasting-adjacent course under the topic that best describes the course. Examples of our classification scheme are provided in Appendix Table 1.3

EF requires concepts from a suite of disciplines. Specifically, we have included four topics that may be more traditionally associated with the humanities and social sciences than the physical sciences: science communication, social sciences, ethics, and traditional ecological knowledge. We include science communication as a foundational topic of EF because, as a field with a particular emphasis on applied research, communicating research and outcomes is an integral component of many applications of EF (Dietze, 2017b). Similarly, topics in the social sciences, including decision science and expert elicitation, offer a structured methodology for scientists interfacing with diverse stakeholders and incorporating many interests into forecasting workflows, while considering ethics (e.g., data science ethics, computer science ethics, ecology ethics) ensures that applications of EF operate within ethical boundaries (e.g., ensuring that data is open source when possible,

crediting knowledge from community members with authorship and acknowledgments). Finally, we strongly believe that any ecological research should incorporate the voices and ways of knowing of all stakeholders in questions of the health and preservation of our natural landscapes. Our forecasting topics include one type of culturally-relevant education under the title “Traditional Ecological Knowledge.” We recognize that by focusing only on Traditional Ecological Knowledge, we omit other categories of culturally relevant educational material (e.g., culturally relevant educational materials for Black and Hispanic students). However, during our data collection, we found no materials at any curriculum level that specifically focused on providing culturally relevant forecasting education to students of minority identities other than Indigenous students. Therefore, we chose to define this topic as “Traditional Ecological Knowledge” instead of “Culturally-relevant Materials” to specifically highlight the lack of materials for students from other minority ethnic/racial backgrounds.

Data Analysis

Our data analysis focused on addressing two components of forecasting education attainability: (1) the distribution of resources among forecasting topics at each curriculum level, and (2) the accessibility of forecasting education in terms of institution type (e.g., the selectivity of the institution). We approached each component with both qualitative and quantitative methods. For all analyses, we derive our conclusions via visual inspection of the data and figures, and confirm our findings using quantitative tests. In this way, both the figures and quantitative methods (described below) should be weighted equally in interpreting our results.

To address the distribution of resources among forecasting topics at each curriculum level (i.e., whether some topics are more represented within the available resources than others), we used χ^2 tests using the *freqtables* package (Cannell, 2020) in the R statistical environment (R version 4.1.2) (R Core Team, 2021). We interpret the χ^2 as indicating that resources are unevenly distributed among forecasting topics when the results are statistically significant (i.e., $p < \alpha$ when $\alpha = 0.05$). Using a graphical representation of the data, we then specifically focused on identifying topics that are overrepresented and underrepresented at each curriculum level. For the purpose of EF curriculum development, the overrepresentation of some topics relative to others suggests that there are sufficient resources available for those topics and additional resource development could focus on other topics. On the other hand, underrepresentation of some topics relative to others highlights gaps to fill with further resource development. We recognize that this analysis oversimplifies the process of curriculum development in two ways. First, how over- and underrepresented topics are defined will change as more educators, who represent more diverse academic interests and underrepresented identities, contribute to EF curriculum development. To this point, we understand that this perspective bears strong assumptions about how curriculum should be developed, which we cover in greater detail in the Discussion and we, additionally, encourage using this framework for further reflection on the state of EF undergraduate curriculum. Second, we do not consider the depth to which topics are covered in each resource, which may lead to an inaccurate characterization of the EF curriculum landscape. For example, if many resources are available for learning about

statistical models, but they do not lead to a comprehensive understanding of how to use statistical modeling for making ecological forecasts, then our methodology would lead to a mischaracterization of the available resources, suggesting that there are sufficient resources for learning about statistical models for undergraduates, when this is not the case. We suggest revisiting our approach with a more detailed analysis of the available resources, including how well the available resources work for learning topics related to EF and not just how many resources exist.

As a second approach to characterizing the availability of resources among curriculum levels, we used Fisher's exact tests to quantify the dissimilarity between different curriculum levels. Specifically, we compared the distribution of resources among forecasting topics between OAORs and forecasting course lessons, and between forecasting-adjacent courses and forecasting course lessons. We compared forecasting course lessons to the other two curriculum levels because forecasting course lessons comprise our best representation of what EF experts believe students should learn to become ecological forecasters. Using the distribution of forecasting course lessons as the "ideal" in this way clearly introduces a bias to our analysis because this approach relies on the perspectives of a limited number of current EF instructors and on forecasting courses taught at both the upper undergraduate and graduate levels. We not only recognize this bias, but embrace it: we strongly advocate for continuing to analyze the distribution of forecasting course lessons among topics and compare the distribution of resources among curriculum levels as more instructors are able to contribute to the distribution of lessons among topics in forecasting courses and as courses are taught more broadly at the undergraduate level. The Fisher's exact test was chosen because this test is similar to a chi-squared test when the dimensions of the contingency matrix are greater than 2x2 but is robust to zero frequencies. Fisher's exact tests were computed using the *freqtables* package (Cannell, 2020), altering the default function to use the hybrid approximation option for large contingency tables and 2,000 Monte Carlo permutations. In this way, we not only considered the distribution of resources within each curriculum level, but also relative to the current standard (i.e., forecasting course lessons) within the sub-field.

We considered the distribution of course-based resources at different curriculum levels among institution types. We assigned each institution a type (e.g., R1 = doctoral universities with very high research activity, B = baccalaureate universities) using Carnegie Classifications, as defined by Indiana University's Carnegie Classification of Institutions of Higher Education database (<https://carnegieclassifications.iu.edu/index.php>). We then grouped the Carnegie Classifications to simplify the interpretation of institution type (see Appendix Table 1.4 for grouping system).

We conducted a logistic regression using the `glm()` function in the *stats* package (R Core Team, 2021) to quantify the difference in forecasting-adjacent course offerings by institution type. Our logistic regression used a binary variable corresponding to institution type A/B vs M/D. The binary classification A/B ($n_{A/B} = 535$) corresponds to the following institution types: Associate's Colleges (A), Associate's/Bachelor's Colleges (A/B), Bachelor's Colleges (B), and Tribal Colleges and Universities (TC). The binary classification M/D ($n_{M/D} = 950$) corresponds to institution types Master's Colleges and Universities–Smaller Programs (M3), Master's Colleges and Universities–Larger Programs (M1), Doctoral Universities–High research activity (R2), Doctoral Universities–Highest

research activity (R1), and Doctoral/Professional Universities (D/PU). The A/B and M/D categories are the response variable in the logistic regression and the forecasting topics into which courses fell are the predictor variables. We used this binary categorization to increase the statistical power of the analysis by including more courses in fewer institution type categories. We grouped tribal colleges (TC) with associate's and baccalaureate institutions (A/B) because the two tribal colleges included in this analysis do not offer degrees higher than bachelor's degrees. We removed the topics "Model Assessment" and "Traditional Ecological Knowledge" from this analysis because only one course was available for each topic, which limited our ability to make inference regarding these topics. We interpret the coefficients of the model as the odds of an institution being an associate's or baccalaureate institution (A/B) relative to a master's or doctoral institution (M/D), given the frequency of offering courses in a given forecasting topic.

Results

The EF Curriculum Landscape Differs by Curriculum Level

Our quantitative analysis of resources for teaching and learning EF reveals differences in how resources are distributed among forecasting topics, with different gaps existing at different curriculum levels (Figure 2). This is expected given inherent differences in how resources are developed at different curriculum levels and for teaching different subjects (see Discussion). The distribution of resources within the forecasting topics is uneven at each curriculum level (OAORs: $\chi^2 = 364$, $df = 18$, $n = 409$, $p < 0.005$; forecasting course lessons: $\chi^2 = 163$, $df = 17$, $n = 192$, $p < 0.005$; forecasting-adjacent courses: $\chi^2 = 2891$, $df = 17$, $n = 1485$, $p < 0.005$), indicating that some topics are more intensively covered than others at each curriculum level. Further, the distribution of forecasting course lessons among the forecasting topics is more even than the distribution of OAORs (Fisher's exact test: $n_{\text{online}} = 409$, $n_{\text{lessons}} = 192$, $p < 0.005$) and forecasting-adjacent courses (Fisher's exact test: $n_{\text{courses}} = 1485$, $n_{\text{lessons}} = 192$, $p < 0.005$). This implies that many topics are over- and underrepresented within OAORs and forecasting-adjacent courses with respect to developing a comprehensive EF curriculum at each of these levels, as defined by evenly covering the topics identified via expert elicitation to comprise an EF education.

For example, a disproportionately high number of open-access online resources are dedicated to basic concepts of computer coding ("Basics of Coding;" Figure 2) relative to both the number of resources dedicated to other topics among OAORs and the number of resources dedicated to basic concepts of computer coding at the other curriculum levels, which undoubtedly reflects the universality of the need for these skills in science careers. Similarly, introductory level ecology courses ("Basics of Ecology") are overrepresented among forecasting-adjacent courses, demonstrating the number of courses specific to ecology offered at many undergraduate-serving institutions. This is expected because introductory courses are applicable to a broader range of degree options than more advanced courses (e.g., introductory ecology courses are often required for undergraduate biology majors). On the other hand, basic concepts of forecasting ("Basics of Forecasting"),

such as what a forecast entails and why prediction is important in the sciences, is an underrepresented topic among both OAORs and forecasting-adjacent courses relative to its representation among forecasting course lessons (Figure 2). Although this is expected given that basic concepts of forecasting are more narrowly applicable to fields involving forecasting, this highlights an opportunity for developing more OAORs specifically on EF, as well as the possibility for incorporating connections to EF into forecasting-adjacent courses.

It is also worth noting that some topics are not represented at all at one or more curriculum levels. Ethical considerations (“Ethics”) in forecasting and in related disciplines (ecology, or computer and data sciences) were not represented in our database of OAORs and only three out of 192 forecasting course lessons in three out of nine courses covers forecasting ethics. This topic highlights important considerations when conducting EF research, including who should be involved in deciding what forecasts are made and whether data should be made publicly available. The forecasting topics (see Appendix Table 1.3), “Science Communication” and “Traditional Ecological Knowledge” are also not represented in forecasting courses. Among our sample of forecasting-adjacent courses, there are no courses specifically covering “Data Assimilation” or “State Space Models.” These topics that are not represented in a curriculum level represent particularly persistent gaps in EF curricula (although lessons on state space models may be incorporated into courses on time series modeling or statistical modeling more broadly). Instructors and EF curriculum developers should bear such persistent gaps in mind when deciding how to allocate limited time and resources to offer students a comprehensive education in EF.

Availability of Forecasting and Forecasting-Adjacent Courses Differs by Institution Type

We next considered whether there are patterns in the availability of resources at the course-based curriculum levels (i.e., forecasting course lessons and forecasting-adjacent courses) across institution types. In general, more forecasting and forecasting-adjacent courses are available at doctoral universities than at colleges and universities offering only associate’s, bachelor’s, or master’s degrees (Figure 3; Table 1). Forecasting courses are currently almost exclusively taught at doctoral universities with very high research activity (institution type R1, $n = 7/9$), while only one forecasting course is taught at an elite baccalaureate institution (institution type B, Smith College; Figure 3B-C) and one is taught outside of the university setting (EFI summer course). This highlights a general need for EF educational opportunities at more diverse higher education institutions in the U.S.

There is more heterogeneity in the type of institutions offering forecasting-adjacent courses than in the institutions offering forecasting courses (Figure 3A). While more forecasting-adjacent courses are offered at master’s and doctoral universities (Figure 3A), other institution types (i.e., offering lower degrees) offer courses corresponding to almost every forecasting topic (Appendix Table 1.3). Specifically, associate’s colleges offer a range of courses relevant to forecasting, particularly within topics associated with computer and data sciences (e.g., “Basics of Statistics,” “Basics of Coding,” “Statistical Models,” “Working with Data,” “Data Manipulation,” “Machine Learning”; Figure 3A). Our logistic regression model offers insight into the topics that forecasting-adjacent courses cover at different types of institutions. Specifically, we interpret the coefficients of our logistic

regression (Table 1) as the odds of an institution being an associate's- or bachelor's-granting institution (A/B) relative to a master's- or doctorate-granting institution (M/D), given the frequency of offering courses of a given forecasting topic. Using this interpretation, three of the six topics indicating a higher odds of an institution being A/B (i.e., offering less advanced degrees) are introductory topics ("Basics of Ecology," "Basics of Forecasting," "Basics of Statistics"), while three are related to more advanced topics ("Ethics," "Machine Learning," "Working with Data"; Table 1). No topics representing advanced quantitative concepts (e.g., "Probability & Uncertainty," "Statistical Models") except "Machine Learning" significantly contribute to the difference between associate's and baccalaureate institutions and master's and doctoral institutions, although two topics ("Data Manipulation" and "Mechanistic Models") are marginally non-significant.

Discussion

Gaps are visible in the existing resources at each curriculum level

Previous literature has discussed the importance of understanding the current curriculum landscape as a first step in improving curriculum in higher education (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021a, 2020; Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018). We identified resources that already exist and highlighted gaps where finite resources could be allocated to build a more comprehensive curriculum in the context of EF. For example, we show that there is a need to introduce high-level quantitative skills (e.g., "Data Assimilation," "Mechanistic Models," "Statistical Models," "Model Assessment") to undergraduate students in forecasting and forecasting-adjacent courses (Figure 2, Appendix). This finding is consistent with previous research indicating that certain data science skills are underrepresented in undergraduate education (Emery et al., 2021) and that undergraduate EES curriculum is an appropriate venue for introducing students to high-level quantitative skills (Barraquand et al., 2014; Carey et al., 2020). This finding also underscores previous research finding that students recognize their own lack of quantitative training in undergraduate ecology curriculum and retroactively desire more training in quantitative concepts and skills (Barraquand et al., 2014), skills which have the potential to improve students' problem solving skills and scientific workforce preparedness (Barraquand et al., 2014; Farrell and Carey, 2018; Hounshell et al., 2021).

Introductory concepts (e.g., "Basics of Ecology," "Basics of Coding") are particularly overrepresented among OAORs and forecasting-adjacent courses. This is relevant because these resources can supplement formal instruction on EF, offering educational opportunities to students without access to forecasting courses. The overrepresentation of introductory concepts is likely because these topics are applicable to many science domains and are not specific to EF. Our survey also helps identify underrepresented advanced topics (e.g., "Data Assimilation," "Model Assessment") to inform potential future resource development to fill the gaps efficiently.

The complete absence of certain forecasting topics ("Ethics," in OAORs; "Science Communication" and "Traditional Ecological Knowledge" in forecasting course lessons; and "Data Assimilation" and "State Space Models" in forecasting-adjacent courses) helps identify gaps where new resources could be developed to offer a more comprehensive suite

of resources to approach EF in the way promoted by EFI. For example, online resources could be developed to allow students to explore the ethical implications of making ecological forecasts. Similarly, topics related to disseminating forecasts to stakeholders (e.g., “Science Communication”) could be incorporated as specific lessons into more forecasting courses or could be offered as forecasting-adjacent courses at more institutions. Finally, the fact that there are few resources for incorporating non-Western ways of knowing into EF courses (“Traditional Ecological Knowledge”) highlights the need for more diverse instructors teaching EF courses and contributing to resource and course development.

Educating undergraduate students is a complex undertaking, meaning that our results should be considered in the context of how students learn. For example, educators understand that some topics can be more suitable to one curriculum level than another. The inclusion of ethics as a lesson within forecasting courses may help students make more connections between ethics and the development of forecasts (Emery et al., 2021; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021b, 2020). Additionally, teaching interdisciplinary topics such as ethics and science communication within forecasting courses is consistent with science instructors’ role and virtue responsibilities (i.e., the responsibilities conferred upon science instructors as science instructors and as moral agents in the practice of teaching science students, respectively) to teach students these topics within the context of the scientific disciplines (Sethy, 2018).

Similar to considering the context in which forecasting topics are taught, by assuming that forecasting course lessons represent the “ideal” distribution of resources among forecasting topics, we recognize that we introduce some bias into our analysis. Specifically, the composition of forecasting courses is heavily dependent upon who is teaching forecasting and which resources the instructors are using to structure their lessons. Similarly, many current EF instructors share resources, such as textbooks and syllabi (e.g., on EFI’s website), contributing to strong non-independence between EF courses in our database. Owing to both the non-independence between EF courses and common demographics between students in EF courses (e.g., mainly graduate students in ecology and environmental sciences, often with prior exposure to quantitative concepts and coding and attending wealthy universities), there may be shared expectations between EF courses regarding the concepts and skills students have prior to the course. For example, many current EF courses expect students to enter EF courses with foundational knowledge in ecology and statistics. We therefore advocate for repeating our approach to analyzing the EF curriculum landscape, and continuing to use forecasting course lessons as the expected distribution of courses, as EF matures as a discipline, when more diverse instructors are teaching forecasting courses and more diverse resources are available from which to build forecasting courses.

Patterns Exist in the Accessibility of Resources at Each Curriculum Level

Equally important to the distribution of existing resources among forecasting topics is the accessibility of resources. Despite being termed open-access, accessibility of OAORs is restricted to students with reliable broadband Internet access and personal computers. Significant portions of students in rural areas, tribal communities, low-income households,

and from traditionally underrepresented racial and ethnic backgrounds are less likely to have reliable Internet and computer access than “traditional” students, who are mainly from urban and suburban, middle class, White households (Dolcini et al., 2021; Sanders and Scanlon, 2021).

Aside from OAORs, the accessibility of courses, both forecasting and forecast-adjacent, is biased towards elite institutions. Based on our representative database of forecasting and forecasting-adjacent courses, we show that all forecasting courses and a substantial portion of forecasting-adjacent courses are taught at doctoral granting institutions with very high research activity (R1 or elite baccalaureate institutions (B; Figure 3, Table 1). We recognize that we may have missed some forecasting courses, especially if they are not labeled as such in course descriptions, and that by analyzing a subsample of all U.S. higher education institutions, we have missed a great deal of forecasting-adjacent courses at unsampled institutions. Nevertheless, our analysis highlights that students living in areas with limited options for higher education (e.g., areas with only community college options; “academic-match education deserts”) may be unable to enroll in forecasting courses (Klasik et al., 2018). This disparity is compounded by the fact that 80% of White Americans enroll in the top 500 higher education institutions, where forecasting courses are more likely to be offered, while 75% of students from underrepresented racial and ethnic backgrounds do *not* enroll in the top 500 institutions (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2021b). This highlights the fact that the racial/ethnic identity and socioeconomic status of students influences the accessibility of forecasting education, disparities which should become a high priority consideration in the development of EF curriculum.

The fact that most advanced topics related to EF (e.g., mechanistic and statistical models, probability and uncertainty) are equally represented at associate’s and bachelor’s-granting institutions compared to master’s and doctoral-granting institutions (Table 1) indicates that advanced quantitative curriculum is similarly developed at both of these institution types. Students at both institution types could benefit from more training in advanced quantitative concepts, consistent with the fact that advanced quantitative concepts tend to be less well represented among forecasting-adjacent courses than introductory concepts (Figure 2). Meanwhile, the fact that fewer forecasting-adjacent introductory courses are available across our subsample of master’s and doctorate-granting institutions highlights that these could benefit from coordination of introductory coursework with partnering two-year institutions (e.g., community college to university programs).

Progress, Limitations, and Future Directions

Current Education Initiatives

Here, we describe several initiatives we have implemented to begin addressing identified gaps in EF education. These initiatives are designed to meet two objectives: (1) increase representation of underrepresented minority students in data science education in the U.S. and (2) increase the number of resources for teaching and learning about high-level quantitative concepts related to ecological forecasting. Native undergraduate students are a subset of underrepresented minority students in the sciences in the U.S., with pervasive

socioeconomic barriers to success in the university context. Consistent with objective (1), we are currently evaluating existing data science and EF resources to address the accessibility of EF education for Native undergraduate students. Specifically, we are evaluating whether (1) materials can be used in low to no Internet environments; (2) materials can be used on mobile devices, the only computers some students have; and (3) materials can be modified to meet technical needs of communities. This initiative has started with considering the needs of students at University of New Mexico, Gallup, a two-year institution with high enrollment of members of the Navajo Nation.

Bridging the gap between objectives (1) and (2), increasing representation of underrepresented minority students and increasing resources for teaching and learning quantitative concepts, we have integrated traditional ecological knowledge into an R Data Analysis course at Salish Kootenai College (SKC). SKC is a tribal college serving members of nearly 70 tribes, making efforts to teach students how to incorporate the questions, issues, and experiences of their communities into applied science (e.g., via ecological forecasting) particularly relevant. Students were taught to use the R statistical computing language to evaluate a large tribal water quality dataset using quantitative statistical analysis, an exercise relevant to the production of mandatory reports that many tribal governments must send to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency annually. Students were also tasked with ranking Traditional Ecological Knowledge values associated with the important spiritual and cultural sites in the watershed being studied. Finally, the students were taught coding strategies that allowed them to combine quantitative and qualitative datasets. Data visualizations of the combined data created new and more powerful ways to evaluate the physical and cultural health of the watershed. By ascribing equal value to both the Western and Native scientific approaches, students' analyses more fully described ecosystem function. This approach encourages students to learn quantitative concepts within a framework that facilitates making connections between coursework and their lives and cultural values.

We address objective (2) by expanding the breadth of resources available for teaching and learning ecological forecasting via Macrosystems EDDIE (Environmental Data-Driven Inquiry and Exploration) modules. Macrosystems EDDIE modules provide students and faculty with hands-on, real-world learning activities to bolster their understanding of macrosystems ecology through modeling and forecasting (MacrosystemsEDDIE.org). The newest four modules (modules 5-8) are primarily focused on teaching macrosystems ecology and EF concepts using National Ecological Observatory Network data (Carey et al., 2020; Farrell and Carey, 2018; Hounshell et al., 2021; Moore et al., 2022). Each of the four forecasting-focused Macrosystems EDDIE modules covers different components of the iterative forecasting cycle, which include building a model, quantifying uncertainty, generating a forecast, communicating a forecast, assessing a forecast, and updating a forecast with observations. For example, in Module 6 "Understanding Uncertainty in Ecological Forecasts," students are introduced to the concept of uncertainty in an ecological forecast and then explore the different sources of forecast uncertainty (e.g., process, parameters, driver data, initial conditions). Second, Module 7, "Improving Forecasts with Data" introduces students to data assimilation with hands-on exercises, potentially bridging the gaps identified in the survey as to the paucity of materials on this topic. Meanwhile, in Module 8, "Using Ecological Forecasts to Guide

Decision Making”, students examine how diverse ecological forecasts are tied to decision-making (e.g., how forecasts of grassland productivity could alter ranch-owners’ decision-making) and components of effective forecast visualizations. Students are introduced to structured decision-making and how stakeholder needs may affect forecast interpretation, addressing another gap we found in the availability of resources related to social science concepts in ecological forecasting.

Future Directions

Coursework, such as forecasting and forecasting-adjacent courses, cannot be fully inclusive without considering in-classroom inclusive best practices (Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018), such as active learning strategies (Corwin et al., 2018; Graham et al., 2013), including culturally relevant examples (Harris et al., 2020), and providing alternative evaluation methods (Miriti, 2019), among others. Our analysis neglected this critical component of EF curriculum by focusing on the courses themselves, rather than the context in which they are taught. Future efforts should include more opportunities for instructors to learn about inclusive pedagogy best practices, opportunities for instructors and forecasting practitioners to discuss barriers to inclusive instruction, and the implementation of working groups aimed toward addressing the identified barriers.

Numerous recent publications have highlighted the necessity of targeted interventions to improve the persistence of students from traditionally underrepresented racial and ethnic groups, including Black, Hispanic, and Indigenous students, in scientific disciplines (Bowser and Cid, 2021; Cheryan et al., 2017). We have undertaken numerous efforts to develop curricula that address the needs of Indigenous students. However, few efforts within the EFI community have focused on the needs of other racial and ethnic minorities, including Black and Hispanic students. Strategies to improve Black and Hispanic student persistence can be similar to those targeting Indigenous students, including the incorporation of Black students’ cultural values into the curriculum (Collins, 2018; Corneille et al., 2020), addressing local community problems through coursework (Corneille et al., 2020), and applying the curriculum to students’ lived experiences (Harris et al., 2020). Future efforts should focus on identifying and implementing strategies for developing EF curriculum that improves Black and Hispanic student persistence, including partnerships with Black and Hispanic educators and forecasting practitioners. Additionally, future EF curriculum development efforts should consider providing resources and courses in languages other than English.

Finally, two-year institutions, such as community colleges, have potential to develop EF programs, according to our analysis of forecasting-adjacent courses. This would benefit a large number of students across diverse backgrounds, as community colleges are growing in attendance in the U.S., where increasing cost of tuition at four-year institutions is reducing the accessibility of four-year degrees for many students (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2020). Partnering ecological forecasters from research-intensive doctoral universities with instructors from community colleges represents an opportunity to increase the accessibility of forecasting education (Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018). To date, we have not engaged with educators and administrators at community colleges in this capacity. Future efforts should include

identifying potential partners at community colleges and considering how forecasting and forecasting-adjacent courses can contribute to two-year degrees and four-year degrees via transfer credits (Rawlings-Goss et al., 2018).

Author Contributions

Alyssa M. Willson: Conceptualization (lead); Methodology (lead); Validation (lead); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (lead); Data curation (lead); Writing—original draft preparation (lead); Writing—review and editing (equal); Visualization (equal). **Hayden Gallo:** Methodology (supporting); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (supporting); Data curation (supporting); Visualization (equal). **Jody A. Peters:** Methodology (supporting); Supervision (equal); Project administration (lead). **Antoinette Abeyta:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting). **Nievita Bueno Watts:** Conceptualization (supporting); Writing—review and editing (supporting). **Cayelan C. Carey:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting); Funding acquisition (equal). **Tadhg N. Moore:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting). **Georgia Smies:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting). **R. Quinn Thomas:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting); Funding acquisition (equal). **Whitney M. Woelmer:** Writing—original draft preparation (supporting). **Jason S. McLachlan:** Writing—review and editing (equal); Supervision (equal); Funding acquisition (equal).

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Data Accessibility

All data presented in this study are available via the Figshare data repository (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.5995435.v1>).

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Figures

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of methodology. **(A)** Each curriculum level reaches a different number of students (x-axis) and covers a different depth of material (y-axis) (See "Descriptions of curricular categories" in Methods). **(B)** Data collection and analysis at each of our three curriculum levels. From left to right, dark blue represents the process of data collection and analysis for open-access, online resources (OAORs), teal represents the process for forecasting course lessons, and light blue represents the process for forecasting-adjacent courses. For each curriculum level, data were collected online via Google (OAORs), course syllabi (forecasting course lessons), or course catalogs (forecasting-adjacent courses). Data were organized into the forecasting topic that best represented the material covered in the resource (multi-headed arrows) and the distribution of resources within each forecasting topic were displayed in pie charts. Black double-headed arrows represent the comparison of the distribution of resources (ecological forecasting curriculum landscape) between forecasting course lessons and OAORs (left) and forecasting course lessons and forecasting-adjacent courses (right). The number of forecasting topics represented in the pie charts is random in this figure and serves only to show that the number of topics can differ by curriculum level.

Figure 2: The ecological forecasting curriculum landscape differs by curriculum level. **(A)** Open-access, online resources (OAORs). **(B)** Lessons in forecasting courses. **(C)** Forecasting-adjacent courses. Colors are the same in all panels and correspond to the figure legend. The slices corresponding to the forecasting topics are in the same order in each panel and correspond to the order of greatest to least number of resources for forecasting course lessons. The colors in each panel are in the same order as in the figure legend, starting from the 12:00 position and moving counterclockwise in the plots and starting from left and moving top to bottom in the legend. Total number of resources in each curriculum level is shown below each panel's title.

Figure 3: Institution type influences the availability of resources in each forecasting topic. Institution type is depicted by a simplification of Carnegie Classification system. Categories in the legend are as follows: A = Associate’s college, A/B = Associate’s/Bachelor’s College, B = Bachelor’s College, D/PU = Doctoral/Professional University, M1 = Master’s Colleges and Universities – Larger Program, M3 = Master’s Colleges and Universities – Smaller Program, R1 = Doctoral University – Very High Research Activity, R2 = Doctoral University – High Research Activity, TC = Tribal College. See Appendix Table 1.4 for the list of institutions per institution type and the Carnegie Classification system. **(A)** The number of forecasting-adjacent courses per institution. Courses per institution was computed by dividing the total number of courses per forecasting topic and institution type by the number of institutions in each institution type. **(B)** Graduate and undergraduate forecasting course lessons per institution. Lessons per institution was computed by dividing the total number of lessons per forecasting topic and institution type by the number of institutions in each institution type. **(C)** Undergraduate forecasting course lessons per institution. As in **(B)**, but only visualizing undergraduate forecasting courses and excluding forecasting courses at the graduate level.

Forecasting Topic	Estimate [95% CI]	p-value
Intercept	1.06 [0.81, 1.38]	0.68
Basics of Ecology	2.24 [1.60, 3.16]	< 0.001
Basics of Forecasting	9.46 [2.10, 42.7]	0.003
Basics of Statistics	1.74 [1.20, 2.51]	0.003
Data Manipulation	1.89 [0.93, 3.84]	0.07
Data Sources	0.89 [0.55, 1.44]	0.63
Data Visualization	1.47 [0.60, 3.61]	0.39
Ethics	8.52 [2.45, 29.6]	< 0.001
Machine Learning	2.68 [1.00, 7.20]	0.05
Mechanistic Models	3.08 [0.95, 9.96]	0.06
Probability & Uncertainty	1.73 [0.61, 4.96]	0.29
Science Communication	1.38 [0.74, 2.55]	0.30
Social Science	1.51 [0.47, 4.89]	0.48
Statistical Models	1.43 [0.92, 2.22]	0.11
Workflows & Open Science	0.38 [0.11, 1.27]	0.11
Working with Data	3.44 [1.65, 7.16]	< 0.001

Table 1: Coefficients from the logistic regression comparing the prevalence of courses in each forecasting topic among associate’s- and bachelor’s-granting institutions (A/B) and master’s- and doctoral-granting institutions (M/D). The left column includes the names of the forecasting topics used to predict the institution type at which the course is offered (either associate’s/baccalaureate institution or master’s/doctoral institution). The middle column includes the coefficient estimates and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) in brackets. The right column includes the p-values of the coefficients, indicating whether the coefficient is significantly different from zero. Rows are shaded gray if the p-value is significant at $\alpha = 0.05$. The p-value for the topic “Machine Learning” is below α before rounding. Coefficients have been exponentiated to represent odds.

Appendix 1: Course Data Collection

We collected data on the availability of resources teaching different topics related to ecological forecasting (EF) at three curriculum levels: (1) open-access, online resources (OAORs), (2) forecasting courses lessons, and (3) forecasting adjacent courses. Here, we describe in more detail the data collection procedures for forecasting course lessons and forecasting adjacent courses. In addition, we provide tables describing the Carnegie classification of the institutions with EF courses (Appendix Table 1.1), the formats of OAORs collected (Appendix Table 1.2), definitions of the forecasting topics (Appendix Table 1.3), and a list of the higher education institutions used to identify forecasting-adjacent courses along with their Carnegie classifications (Appendix Table 1.4).

Forecasting Course Lessons

Forecasting courses were identified using a published table of EF courses from the Ecological Forecasting Initiative's (EFI's) website (<https://ecoforecast.org/resources/educational-resources/>). The course list is up-to-date as of March 18, 2022, although some forecasting courses have not been included on the website for several reasons. First, EFI may be unaware of some EF courses by instructors not integrally involved in EFI. Second, EFI has been unable to obtain course information and/or syllabi from some courses. However, the courses available on EFI's website are many of the first EF courses offered in the U.S., making them a reliable foundation by which to analyze the state of EF education at its beginning.

Of the 17 forecasting courses available on the EFI website as of March 18, 2022, we excluded eight courses. First, we excluded the syllabus titled "Ecological Forecasting and Informatics 2019" taught by Michael Dietze because an updated syllabus from the same course is available under "Ecological Forecasting and Informatics 2021" also taught by Michael Dietze. Second, we excluded the courses titled "ESPM-288: Reproducible & Collaborative Data Science" taught by Carl Boettiger and "Ecological Forecasting Seminar" taught by Brett Melbourne because these courses were taught in a highly unstructured format centered around student projects, making data collection on each course lesson impossible. Third, we excluded the course "An Overview of Structured Decision Making - ALC3183 - Resources" taught by Michael Runge and Sarah Converse because this course is specifically on structured decision making, which is only one component of EF and not representative of a full EF education. Fourth, we excluded the course "Dinámica Ecológica y Predicciones (Ecological Dynamics and Predictions)" taught by Peter Adler and Juan Manuel Morales because this is the same course as another one on the list, but taught in Spanish. Finally, we excluded the courses "Quantitative Ecology and Evolution," "Machine Learning for Ecology," and "Data Science for Biological Research"

taught by Brett Melbourne because these courses are not specifically on EF, but cover environmental data science more broadly. This left us with a total of nine EF courses.

For each of the nine EF courses, we categorized each course lesson into one of the forecasting topics we defined. Course lessons were defined using the topic of instruction for each calendar date in the syllabus. Some dates were excluded. Introductory lessons (e.g., “Introduction”) and concluding lessons (e.g., “Concluding remarks”) were excluded if there was no associated text or assignment that would indicate that the lesson included teaching related to EF. Any dates that indicated that there was no class (e.g., “Independent work time,” “Class canceled,” “Break”) were excluded. Any catch-up lessons (e.g., “Answering questions,” “Ask me anything”) were excluded.

Some courses required modifications to data collection specific to that course. In the case of the course titled “Topics in Statistical and Data Sciences - Ecological Forecasting,” the nine course periods related to course projects were combined into three lessons, one for each of the groups: “Parameter Estimation,” “Time Series Forecasting,” and “Wildfire Biomass Estimation” because each group presented three updates. For “Ecological Dynamics and Forecasting,” each bullet titled “Discussion,” “Lecture,” or “Lab” was considered its own lesson because this was the finest resolution for which we could assign a forecasting topic. For “Topics in Ecological Forecasting,” the topic of each lesson was determined from the chapter of the course’s associated textbook that was to be read for each class period. Finally, lessons for the course titled “NEFI 2020 Short Course” were determined according to the blocks of time on the calendar (e.g., blocks of one- to two-hour intervals) instead of by calendar date because the course is only one week in duration. Additionally, only lectures were included for this short course.

For each forecasting course, we recorded the URL to the syllabus, the course name, the instructor’s name, the institution at which the course was taught, the education level at which the course was offered (i.e., undergraduate, graduate, or mixed undergraduate/graduate) based on the institution’s course numbering system and the course description, and the Carnegie Classification of the institution.

Due to the small sample size of EF courses, our data includes a mixture of graduate, undergraduate, and mixed graduate-undergraduate courses. We consider the impact of including both graduate and undergraduate courses in the analysis by including separate visualizations for all courses and only undergraduate courses.

EF Course Search

We conducted an additional search for potential EF courses within the course catalogs of U.S. land grant institutions in order to ensure that our method of collecting forecasting course syllabi from EFI’s website did not bias our results. We focused on land grant institutions because these institutions are a subset of all higher education institutions

in the U.S. and include institutions of multiple Carnegie classifications (e.g., including high research intensity doctoral universities, community colleges, tribal colleges). A complete list of land grant institutions can be found via the National Institute of Food and Agriculture's website (<https://www.nifa.usda.gov/about-nifa/how-we-work/partnerships/land-grant-colleges-universities>). We searched each of the institutions listed on the National Institute of Food and Agriculture's website (<https://www.nifa.usda.gov/about-nifa/how-we-work/partnerships/land-grant-colleges-universities>), including all campuses in the University of California and University of Hawaii systems, except for D-Q University, which lost accreditation in 2005.

For each institution, we searched the most recent course catalog for the term "forecast*" among course titles and descriptions. We then evaluated each instance of the term "forecast*" for its applicability to EF. We excluded courses related to business/financial forecasting, weather forecasting, hydrological forecasting, and statistical forecasting, as determined by course descriptions, because these courses did not relate to EF.

We contacted the instructors of courses that we interpreted as potentially teaching EF to request a recent syllabus for these courses. In total, we identified fourteen potential EF courses among 129 land grant institutions. Among the fourteen potential EF courses, four courses were excluded because the instructor(s) did not respond to our request, three courses were excluded because the instructor(s) declined to provide a syllabus, two courses were determined to be on the topic of hydrologic forecasting, one course was determined to be on the topic of economic/price forecasting, one course was considered not on EF by the instructor, and two were determined to not emphasize forecasting by inspecting the course syllabi (one on climate science and one on ecological modeling). We concluded that we could reasonably assume that the EF courses available on EFI's website represent the breadth of EF courses available at the time of analysis in the U.S.

Forecasting Adjacent Courses

Data on forecasting-adjacent courses were collected by looking at the course catalogs of a random sample of higher education institutions in the U.S. Institutions were identified using a published list from *The Advocate* of all higher education institutions in the U.S., including four-year public and private institutions, two-year institutions (e.g., community colleges, technical colleges), tribal colleges, and for-profit institutions.

A small number of institutions were excluded. Some institutions (Carnegie Science, South Central Career Center, Fortis Institute, University of Tennessee Health Science Center, Notre Dame de Namur University) were excluded because they do not offer degrees at the undergraduate level (i.e., associate's, bachelor's) and/or do not offer undergraduate

degrees that are applicable to EF. Two institutions randomly selected from our list had closed (Concordia College New York, Concordia University Portland, Oregon) and one institution had merged with another institution (Austin Graduate School of Theology) since the publication of the list of higher education institutions in 2018. One institution (California Institute of Integral Studies) only offered options to finish undergraduate-level degrees, rather than offering an entire degree program. Our final random sample included 48 higher education institutions.

For each institution, we located the most recent course catalog on the institution's website. We then read the course name and description for every undergraduate course offered. We identified forecasting-adjacent courses by determining whether a course was related to one of the forecasting topics. For example, a course titled "Data Visualization" can be categorized under the forecasting topic by the same name. For more examples, see Appendix Table 1.3. Each course applicable to EF was only categorized into one forecasting topic, even if multiple topics might be applicable. If more than one forecasting topic was applicable to a given course, the topic that appeared most central to the mission of the course (e.g., by course name, emphasis on course description) was chosen. For how specific courses were classified, we refer the reader to the data available on [Figshare](#).

Some courses were systematically excluded from our dataset. Introductory biology courses (e.g., "General Biology") without a specific emphasis on ecology were excluded because we considered them more basic than what is necessary for an EF education. Similarly, biology (e.g., "Botany," "Zoology") and forestry (e.g., "Forest Resource Management") courses not specific to ecology were excluded from the "Basics of Ecology" topic. Calculus courses more advanced than Calculus I were excluded because they are more advanced than what is required for an EF education. Finally, courses offered only at the high school or graduate level and courses offered for zero credits were excluded because we were interested in courses that could contribute to an undergraduate EF degree program.

Carnegie Classification	Type	Institutions Included
Baccalaureate Colleges: Arts & Sciences Focus	B	Smith College
R1: Doctoral Universities – Very High Research Activity	R1	Boston University
		University of California, Berkeley
		University of California, Santa Cruz
		University of Colorado, Boulder
		University of Florida
		University of Notre Dame
		Utah State University
		Virginia Tech*
NA	NA	Ecological Forecasting Initiative Summer Course

Appendix Table 1.1: Carnegie Classifications for, simplified institution types for, and portion of the analysis in which each of the eleven forecasting courses was used. The left column contains Carnegie Classifications from Indiana University’s database, the second column includes our simplified institution type, the third column includes each institution hosting an ecological forecasting course, and the final column includes the portion of the analysis in which each course was used. Note that two courses did not have sufficiently detailed syllabi to be used to analyze the distribution of lessons among forecasting topics (Portion of Analysis: Geographic only) and one course was taught outside of the university setting and thus was not included in the geographic analysis (Portion of Analysis: Forecasting topic only). All other courses were used in both parts of the analysis (Portion of Analysis: Forecasting topic; Geographic). * denotes multiple courses taught at the same institution.

Material Type	Definition
Article	Online short texts
Course Material	Archived material from past synchronous or asynchronous academic course
External Repository	Links to other collections of resources (e.g., QUBES)
Module	Short, hands-on lessons
NetLogo Lab	Module dependent on NetLogo software
Textbook	Full online textbooks
Video	Recorded lectures, video tutorials, etc.
Workshop	Recurring synchronous learning opportunity

Appendix Table 1.2: Types of open-access, online resources (OAORs) included in our database.

Forecasting Topic	Definition	Example
Basics of Coding	Introduction to programming languages used in quantitative ecology	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Programming in R”
Basics of Ecology	Introduction to basic ecological concepts	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Ecology and the Environment”
Basics of Forecasting	Introduction to the utility and general structure of ecological forecasts	Forecasting course lesson titled “The Iterative Forecasting Cycle”
Basics of Statistics	Introduction to statistical methods	Online video titled “State Space Models”
Data Assimilation	Introduction to techniques for formally combining data with model predictions	Online video titled “Introduction to Particle Filters”
Data Manipulation	Resources for learning how to format, manipulate, and process data for analysis	Forecasting course lesson titled “Tidy Data with Tidyverse”
Data Sources	Resources for learning how to acquire data used in ecological forecasting	Forecasting course lesson titled “Acquiring Satellite Data”
Data Visualization	Resources for making figures and graphics to represent data and forecasts	Online video titled “Plotting Trendlines with ggplot”
Ethics	Introduction to ethical considerations related to ecological forecasting, data science, and related disciplines	Forecasting course lessons titled “Guidelines for Deciding When to Publish Your Data”
Machine Learning	Introduction to machine learning techniques for ecological forecasting	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Introduction to Machine Learning”
Mechanistic Models	Introduction to developing and interpreting process-driven models	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Introduction to Earth System Modeling”
Model Assessment	Introduction to techniques for assessing mechanistic and statistical model performance	Online article titled “Interpretation of Akaike and Bayesian Information Criteria”
Probability & Uncertainty	Resources for working with and interpreting probability-based uncertainty	Forecasting course lesson titled “Uncertainty Partitioning”
Science Communication	Resources for learning how to communicate science to audiences within and outside of the academy (e.g., policymakers)	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Science Writing”
Social Science	Introduction to social science concepts related to either expert elicitation or making informed policy	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Structured Decision Making”

	and management decisions using ecological forecasts	
State Space Models	Introduction to the specific class of statistical models of state space models	Forecasting course lesson titled “Using State Space Models”
Traditional Ecological Knowledge	Introduction to the incorporation of Traditional Ecological Knowledge with Western scientific knowledge	Online module titled “Native Case Studies in Conservation”
Workflows & Open Science	Resources for learning how to make reproducible workflows	Online module titled “Basic Github Commands”
Statistical Models	Introduction to developing and interpreting statistical models	Forecasting-adjacent course titled “Applied Linear Models”
Working with Data	Resources with hands-on practice working with actual data sets	Online module titled “Analyzing Eddy Covariance Data”

Appendix Table 1.3: Forecasting topics and their definitions. All open-access, online resources (OAORs), forecasting course lessons, and forecasting-adjacent courses were classified into forecasting topics. A theoretical example of each topic is provided in the right column.

Carnegie Classification	Type	Institutions Included
Associate's Colleges: High Career & Technical – High Nontraditional	A	Chippewa Valley Technical College Gateway Technical College Neosho County Community College Walla Walla Community College
Associate's Colleges: Mixed Transfer/Career & Technical – High Nontraditional		Garden City Community College Mid-Plains Community College
Associate's Colleges: Mixed Transfer/Career & Technical – High Traditional		Copper Mountain College Delta College Guilford Technical Community College
Associate's Colleges: High Career & Technical – High Traditional		Del Mar College Lamar State College – Port Arthur
Associate's Colleges: High Transfer – Mixed Traditional/Nontraditional		Illinois Central College
Associate's Colleges: High Transfer – High Traditional		Diablo Valley College Mineral Area College
Associate's Colleges: Mixed Transfer/Career & Technical – Mixed Traditional/Nontraditional		City College of San Francisco San Bernardino Valley College
Associate's Colleges: High Transfer – High Nontraditional		Central Oregon Community College
Associate's – Public Urban-serving Single Campus		Cedar Valley College
Baccalaureate/Associate's Colleges: Associate's Dominant		A/B
Baccalaureate/Associate's Colleges: Mixed Baccalaureate/Associate's	Vermont Technical College	
Baccalaureate Colleges: Diverse Fields	B	Culver-Stockton College Goshen College University of Arkansas at Pine Bluff

Baccalaureate Colleges: Arts & Sciences Focus		Centenary College of Louisiana Swarthmore College Vassar College
M3: Master's Colleges and Universities – Smaller Programs	M3	Eastern Connecticut State University University of Tennessee Martin University of Wisconsin Stevens Point
M1: Master's Colleges and Universities – Larger Programs	M1	Clarion University Fitchburg State University Lynn University Nyack College Saint Francis University
D/PU: Doctoral/Professional Universities	D/PU	Alliant International University Fresno State University of Charleston University of Saint Joseph Connecticut University of Texas at Tyler
R2: Doctoral Universities – High Research Activity	R2	Eastern Michigan University New Mexico State University Rochester Institute of Technology Thomas Jefferson University University of Alaska Fairbanks
R1: Doctoral Universities – Very High Research Activity	R1	Auburn University University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign
Tribal Colleges	TC	Blackfeet Community College United Tribes Technical College

Appendix Table 1.4: Carnegie Classifications and simplified institution types for each of the 48 higher education institutions used in our analysis of forecasting-adjacent courses. The left column contains Carnegie Classifications from Indiana University's database, the middle column groups the Carnegie Classifications into a simplified system including only nine institution types, and the right column contains each institution included in our analysis.